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Synthesis of Steroidal and Terpenoidal Extranucleo *N*-Phenyloxazolidinones

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3-[4'-Oxo-3'-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolidin-2'-ylidenehydrazino]-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1d), 3-[4'-oxo-3'-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolidin-2'-ylidenehydrazino]lanosta-8,24-diene

1

- 1; R=3 α -OH; 3 β -H
 2 3; R=3 β -OH; 3 α -H
 1a, 2a, 3a; R=O
 1b, 2b, 3b; R=N-NH₂
 1c, 2c, 3c; R=N-NH-CO-NHPh

2

3

(2d) and 3-[4'-oxo-3'-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolidin-2'-ylidenehydrazino]olean-12-ene (3d) have been prepared in four steps from appropriate steroid/terpenoid alcohols. Oxazolidinones have been found to be associated with a wide spectrum of biological activities¹. In view of this we have undertaken the synthesis of steroidal and terpenoidal oxazolidinones. In present investigation *N*-phenyloxazolidinone ring was built up on C-3 of bile acid, lithocholic acid (1), tetracyclic triterpene, lanosterol (2) and pentacyclic triterpene, β amyrin (3).

3 α -Hydroxy-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1) on oxidation with Jones reagent gave 3-oxo-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1a). Oxidation of 3 β -hydroxylanosta-8,24-diene (2) and 3 β -hydroxyolean-12-ene (3) with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex² gave lanosta-8,24-dien-3-one (2a) and olean-12-en-3-one (3a) respectively. The reaction of 1a, 2a and 3a with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution gave the respective 3-hydrazones (1b, 2b, 3b), which when refluxed with phenyl isocyanate in benzene solution gave the respective *N*-phenylsemicarbazones (1c, 2c, 3c).

The cyclisation of 1c, 2c and 3c with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished 3-[4'-oxo-3'-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolidin-2'-ylidenehydrazino]-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1d), 3-[4'-oxo-3'-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolidin-2'-ylidenehydrazino]lanosta-8,24-diene (2d), 3-[4'-oxo-3'-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolidin-2'-ylidenehydrazino]olean-12-ene (3d) respectively. The ¹³C nmr spectral data of the compounds were assigned by comparison with the spectra of 5 β -cholan-24-oic acid derivatives³, lanostan-3 β ol derivatives⁴, olean-12-ene derivatives⁵ and oxazolidinone derivatives⁶.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137

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spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a JEOL FX-90 Q FT instrument with TMS as internal standard and ^{13}C nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a JEOL JNN FX-100 (25.00 Mz) spectrometer (temp. 25°) using TMS as internal standard. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction of b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$. Jones reagent was prepared from CrO_3 (5.2 g), H_2SO_4 (5 ml) and water (20 ml).

Chromium trioxide-pyridine complex was prepared by the literature procedure².

3-Oxo-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1a): To a solution of 3 α -hydroxy-5 β -cholan-24-oic acid (1; 3 g) in acetone (100 ml) was added 8*N* Jones reagent at 0° dropwise until the orange colour of the reagent persisted. Excess of the chromium trioxide was then destroyed by the addition of 2-propanol (5 ml) and the precipitated chromium salts were removed by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated to yield a residue which was crystallised from methanol, (90%, 2.68 g), m.p. $121\text{--}22^\circ$; ν_{max} 1 715 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) 1 250 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$).

Lanosta-8,24-dien-3-one (2a) and olean-12-en-3-one (3a): To a solution of 2/3 (5 g) in methylene chloride (150 ml), was added chromium trioxide-pyridine complex (35 g) as a slurry in methylene chloride (50 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. The tarry solid was then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute HCl (5%), sodium bicarbonate (5%), water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent gave a semisolid which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (50 g). The ether-petroleum ether (1 : 3) eluate gave a solid which was crystallised from methanol to yield 2a (65%), m.p. $82\text{--}83^\circ$; 3a (72%), $185\text{--}87^\circ$; ν_{max} 1 710 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 630–1 590 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 1 245 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$).

The hydrazones (1b, 2b, 3b): A mixture of the ketone (1a, 2a, 3a; 2.5 g), hydrazine hydrochloride (0.1 g) and freshly distilled hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The excess of solvent was then distilled off and the residual solution was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol; 1b (78%), m.p. $270\text{--}72^\circ$; 2b (78%), $174\text{--}76^\circ$; 3b (80%), $106\text{--}07^\circ$; ν_{max} 3 300, 3 150 (NH_2) and 1 480 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$).

The *N*-phenylsemicarbazones (1c, 2c, 3c): To the hydrazone (1b, 2b, 3b; 1.5 g) in benzene (50 ml) was added phenyl isocyanate (2 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. Benzene was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oil which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (40 g). The benzene-petroleum ether (3 : 2) eluate gave a solid which was crystallised from methanol to yield 1c (79%), m.p. $210\text{--}12^\circ$; 2c (82%), $184\text{--}86^\circ$; 3c (83%), $205\text{--}07^\circ$; ν_{max} 3 300

(NH), 1 680 (CONH), 1 620–1 580 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 1 470 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$); δ 8.1 (1H, br s, NHCO), 7.6 (5H, m, ArH) and 6.4 (1H, br s, NHPH).

The *N*-phenyloxazolidinones (1d, 2d, 3d): A mixture of the *N*-phenylsemicarbazone (1c, 2c, 3c; 1 g) and chloroacetic acid (0.25 g) was refluxed in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (0.25 g) and acetic acid (30 ml) for 6–8 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the concentrated solution was poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate (5%), water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent furnished a semisolid which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g). Elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) afforded the product which was recrystallised from methanol: 1d (61%), m. p. $162\text{--}63^\circ$; ν_{max} 1 715 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 640–1 590 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1 480 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1 250 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$); pmr δ 7.6 (5H, m, ArH), 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2 of oxazolidinone), 0.98 (3H, d, J 6 Hz $\text{C}_{21}\text{-H}_3$), 0.92 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{19}\text{-H}_3$), 0.68 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{15}\text{-H}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ 218.5 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 175.2 (COOH), 158.2 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 132.8, 128.7, 128.3, 126.8 (ArC), 69.5 (CH_2 of oxazolidinone), 12.2 (C-18), 23.2 (C-19), 18.1 (C-21), 31.4 (C-23); 2d (63%), m. p. $132\text{--}33^\circ$; ν_{max} 1 710 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 630–1 590 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1 480 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1 245 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$); pmr δ 7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 4.55 (2H, s, CH_2 of oxazolidinone), 5.14 (1H, t, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 0.70 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{15}\text{-H}_3$), 1.10 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{19}\text{-H}_3$), 0.90 (3H, d, J 6.3 Hz, $\text{C}_{21}\text{-H}_3$), 1.07 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{23}\text{-H}_3$), 1.04 (1H, m, 5-H), 0.94 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{29}\text{-H}_3$), 0.85 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{30}\text{-H}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ 218.9 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 157.6 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 132.4, 128.7, 128.3, 126.8 (ArC), 69.2 (CH_2 of oxazolidinone), 134.3 (C-8), 134.5 (C-9), 16.1 (C-18), 19.1 (C-19), 18.8 (C-21), 125.2 (C-24), 130.6 (C-25), 24.2 (C-28), 28.1 (C-29), 25.7 (C-30); 3d (63%), m. p. $148\text{--}50^\circ$; ν_{max} 1 710 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 630–1 590 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1 470 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1 245 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}$); pmr δ 7.46 (5H, m, ArH), 4.54 (2H, s, CH_2 of oxazolidinone), 5.18 (1H, t, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 1.05 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{15}\text{-H}_3$), 1.03 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{19}\text{-H}_3$), 1.10 (6H, s, $\text{C}_{23}\text{-H}_3$, $\text{C}_{26}\text{-H}_3$), 1.16 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{27}\text{-H}_3$), 0.82 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{29}\text{-H}_3$), 0.90 (6H, s, $\text{C}_{29}\text{-H}_3$, $\text{C}_{30}\text{-H}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ 218.6 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 158.4 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$), 132.7, 128.9, 128.5, 127.0 (ArC), 69.4 (CH_2 of oxazolidinone), 121.7 (C-12), 145.1 (C-13), 27.8 (C-23), 15.9 (C-24), 15.6 (C-25), 16.8 (C-26), 26.2 (C-27), 28.2 (C-28), 33.2 (C-29), 23.6 (C-30).

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